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GENERAL CLASSIFICATION OF DISEASES OF THE GALLBLADDER AND CHILDREN'S TRACT

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the data on the general classification of diseases of the gallbladder and children's tract. According to traditional concepts, bile accumulates in the gallbladder between digestive processes and enters the duodenum after the stimulating effect of the food consumed. Recent studies show that bile flow is a constant process, and the emptying of the gallbladder occurs constantly. The factors responsible for filling and emptying the gallbladder are hormonal, nervous and mechanical. Digestion of food leads to the release of the duodenal hormone - cholecystokinin, the main stimulator of emptying the gallbladder, and fat is the strongest irritation.

Key words: food, gallbladder, factor, disease, understanding, analysis, bile flow, intestinal

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ОБЩАЯ КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ЖЕЛЧНОГО ПУЗЫРЯ И ДЕТСКОГО ТРАКТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье проанализированы данные по общей классификации заболеваний желчного пузыря и детского тракта. Согласно традиционным представлениям, желчь накапливается в желчном пузыре в межпищеварительный период и поступает в двенадцатиперстную кишку после стимулирующего действия принятой пищи. Результаты современных исследований свидетельствуют о том, что желчеистечение представляет собой

непрерывный процесс, и опорожнение желчного пузыря происходит постоянно. Факторами, ответственными за наполнение и опорожнение желчного пузыря, являются гормональные, нервные и механические. Прием пищи приводит к выбросу в двенадцатиперстной кишке гормона – холецистокинина, являющегося основным стимулятором опорожнения желчного пузыря, а наиболее сильным раздражителем является жир.

Ключевые слова: пища, желчный пузырь, фактор, заболевание, понимание, анализ, желчеистечение, кишечный.

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O'T PUFAGI VA BOLALAR TRAKTI KASALLIKLARINING UMUMIY TASNIFI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada o't pufagi va bolalar trakti kasalliklarining umumiy tasnifi bo'yicha ma'lumotlar tahlil qilinadi. An'anaviy tushunchalarga ko'ra, safro o't pufagida ovqat hazm qilish davrida to'planib, qabul qilingan ovqatning ogohlantiruvchi ta'siridan keyin o'n ikki barmoqli ichakka kiradi. Zamonaviy tadqiqotlar natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, o't pufagi doimiy jarayon bo'lib, o't pufagining bo'shatilishi doimiy ravishda sodir bo'ladi. O't pufagini to'ldirish va bo'shatish uchun javobgar bo'lgan omillar gormonal, asabiy va mexanikdir. Ovqatlanish o'n ikki barmoqli ichakda o't pufagini bo'shatishning asosiy stimulyatori bo'lgan xoletsistokinin gormoni chiqarilishiga olib keladi va eng kuchli tirnash xususiyati beruvchi yog ' hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: oziq-ovqat, o't pufagi, omil, kasallik, tushunish, tahlil qilish, o't yo'llari, ichak.

INTRODUCTION

The gallbladder and biliary tract are responsible for storing and releasing bile, a fluid that aids in the digestion of fats. Diseases of the gallbladder and biliary tract can affect people of all ages, but they are most common in adults. In children, diseases of the gallbladder and biliary tract are rare, but they can be serious.

The gallbladder, also known as the vesica fellea, is a bag-shaped organ with a distinctive dark green color. It is located inside the liver's fossa, or inner surface, and connects to the fibrous membrane through loose fiber. It is 8–14 centimeters long. It stores bile, a fluid that is produced by the liver and helps to digest fats. The biliary tract is a system of ducts that carries bile from the liver to the gallbladder and then to the small intestine.

The gallbladder is made up of the neck (collum vesicae felleae), which is the narrowest portion and where the cystic duct exits, and the bottom (fundus vesicae felleae), which is the widest part of the body (corpus vesicae felleae), which is the middle part. The liver's lower portion is reached by the gallbladder's bottom, and the liver's gate is reached by the neck. A bend is created in the neck where the body meets it.

The free surface of the gallbladder is covered by the serous membrane. The layer of loose connective tissue on the upper wall of the gallbladder that is not covered by the peritoneum is called the tela subserosa vesicae, and it lies underneath the serous base.

The gallbladder's muscular membrane is composed of a single, circular layer of smooth muscles, which include bundles of fibers positioned obliquely and longitudinally. In the neck region, the muscular layer is the thickest.

The gallbladder mucous membrane is bordered by a single-row columnar epithelium. It takes the form of numerous tiny folds called plicae tunicae mucosae vesicae felleae, which give it the appearance of a network. Obliquely oriented spiral folds, known as plicae spirales, develop in the neck region. The glands are situated in a submucosa that covers the torso and neck.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The absorption function of the gallbladder. This is the main task of concentrating bile by absorbing water and sodium. The gallbladder is able to concentrate intermediate ingredients in the liver bile (5-10 factors) and reduce their volume by 80-90%. Although the gallbladder mainly serves as an absorbing organ, mucus secretion is noted by it, which occurs in pathological conditions such as the gallbladder's stone accumulation and intermittent obstruction of the cyst canal.

Motor activity of the gallbladder and biliary tract. According to traditional concepts, bile accumulates in the gallbladder between digestive processes and enters the duodenum after the stimulating effect of the food consumed. Recent studies show that bile flow is a constant process, and the emptying of the gallbladder occurs constantly. The factors responsible for filling and emptying the gallbladder are hormonal, nervous and mechanical. Digestion of food leads to the release of the duodenal hormone - cholecystokinin, the main stimulator of emptying the gallbladder, and fat is the strongest irritation. Cholecystokinin receptors have been identified in the smooth muscles of the gallbladder. Maximum discharge occurs within 90-120 minutes after meals. Motilin, secretin, histamine and prostaglandins have different effects on the contraction of the gallbladder. Cholinergic stimulation is the primary nerve factor responsible for controlling the gallbladder's motor activity, hence inducing contraction. When the gallbladder's pressure level—which is influenced by bile flow and sphincter pressure—rises over the gallbladder cavity's pressure level, the gallbladder fills up. This process can be influenced by many intestinal peptides as endogenous factors.

Motor activity of the Oddi sphincter and biliary tract. The timing of the gallbladder's contraction and the Oddi sphincter's relaxation determines how much bile flows to the duodenum. The release of cholecystokinin, stimulated by food intake, reduces the phasic activity of the contraction of the Oddi sphincter and causes relaxation, thereby ensuring the outflow of bile into the duodenum.

Formation of bile. Bile is mainly composed of water, organic lipids, and usually electrolytes secreted by hepatocytes. The composition of bile electrolytes is similar to that of extracellular fluid. The concentration of proteins in bile is relatively low. Organic components are bile salts, cholesterol and phospholipids. The liver uses cholesterol to create the two primary bile acids, chenodeoxycholic and cholic. In the liver, it is conjugated with either taurine or glycine ester. Much of the cholesterol found in bile is synthesized in the liver de novo. Bile acids are important endogenous regulators of cholesterol metabolism. Bile acids in food inhibit the synthesis of cholesterol in the liver, but increase its absorption. Lecithin accounts for about 90% of all phospholipids in human bile. Enterohepatic circulation of bile acids. About 80% of conjugated bile acids are actively absorbed in the terminal segment of the lateral intestine. After absorption, the portal circulation transports all bile acids from the intestine back to the liver. This system allows a relatively small pool of bile salts to be processed 6-12 times a day with minimal waste during each cycle. Only 5% of bile salts are excreted in the feces.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section we will present different types of classifications of diseases of the gallbladder and children's tract. Diseases of the children's tract can be classified into two main categories:

Congenital disorders: These disorders are present at birth. Congenital disorders include:

- Biliary atresia: This is a condition in which the bile ducts are blocked or absent. Biliary atresia can lead to liver failure.
- Choledochal cyst: This is a condition in which the bile duct is dilated. Choledochal cyst can cause pain, jaundice, and other symptoms.

Acquired disorders: These disorders develop after birth. Acquired disorders include:

- Gallstones: Gallstones can form in children, but they are less common than in adults. Gallstones can cause pain, nausea, and vomiting.

- Cholecystitis: Cholecystitis can occur in children, but it is less common than in adults. Cholecystitis can be caused by gallstones, bacteria, or other factors.
- Cholangitis: Cholangitis can occur in children, but it is less common than in adults. Cholangitis can be caused by gallstones, bacteria, or other factors.

Diseases of the gallbladder can be classified into two main categories:

Functional disorders: These disorders affect the function of the gallbladder, but they do not cause any structural damage. Functional disorders include:

- Biliary dyskinesia: This is a disorder of the muscles that control the gallbladder. It can cause pain, nausea, and vomiting.
- Acalculous cholecystitis: This is an inflammation of the gallbladder that is not caused by gallstones.

Organic disorders: These disorders cause structural damage to the gallbladder. Organic disorders include:

- Cholelithiasis: This is the presence of gallstones in the gallbladder. Gallstones can cause pain, nausea, and vomiting.
- Cholecystitis: This is an inflammation of the gallbladder that is caused by gallstones.
- Cholangitis: This is an inflammation of the bile ducts. Cholangitis can be caused by gallstones, bacteria, or other factors.

Classification of diseases of the bile system: In the group of diseases of the gallbladder, A. L. Myasnikov independently distinguishes dyskinesia, infectious lesions of the gallbladder (syphilis, tuberculosis, brucellosis, etc.) along with cholecystitis, gallbladder tumors and parasitic diseases. The classification of diseases of the bile system, presented by S. Fedorov, is based on pathological and etiological principles:

1. With acute primary cholecystitis results:

- a) complete restoration;
- b) Primary drops;
- c) secondary (inflammatory) drops.

2. Chronic uncomplicated cholecystitis:

- a) purulent cholecystitis;
- b) wounded;
- c) gangrenous cholecystitis;
- d) gallbladder empyema.

3. Bladder sclerosis.

4. Actinomycosis of the bladder.

5. Bladder tuberculosis.

6. Inflammation of the bile ducts;

- subacute cholangitis;

- acute cholangitis;

- purulent cholangitis,

M. Studenikin's classification:

1. Inflammatory patients.

2. Patients with giardiasis of the gallbladder and biliary tract.

3. Patients with inflammation and giardiasis lesions.

4. Patients with biliary dyskinesia.

JKB classification (Ilchenko AA, 2002)

Classification by D.M. Small (1974):

Stage I-genetic, biochemical and metabolic defects that lead to saturation of bile cholesterol;

Phase II-chemical: in the biochemical study of bile, the symptoms of lithogenic bile are identified;

Stage III-physical: cholesterol crystals are formed;

Stage IV-crystal growth and formation of cholesterol stones;

Stage V-make a remuneration of clinical signs of cholelithiasis.Hh Mansurov (1982) identified two periods in the classification of gallstone disease-pre-clinical and clinical - with three stages of the course:

Stage I-violation of the physicochemical properties of bile as a result of the secretion of lithogenic bile by the liver; there are no clinical manifestations of gallstone disease;

Phase II-the formation of gallstones that continue without clear clinical manifestations;

Stage III-surgery; according to the author, the phenomena of obturation are characteristic of this stage. In the CGB classification, Yu.M. Dederer et al. (1983) identified the following forms:

- hidden;
- dyspeptic;
- painful chronic;
- biliary colic and chronic relapse;
- others (angina pectoris, Saint syndrome).

Clinical forms of gallstone disease according to S.A . Dasvani, et al. et al. (2000):

- hidden (stone bearing);
- primary chronic cholecystitis;
- liver (biliary) colic;
- chronic recurrent calculous cholecystitis;
- chronic residual cholecystitis;
- other forms (angina pectoris, Saint syndrome).

Working classification of JKB II Degtyareva and IN Skrypnik (2000) suggests the following.

1. Chronic cholecystitis with lithogenic properties of bile (physicochemical stage of cholesterol or mixed calculus).

2. Surgical stage of calculous cholecystitis (GLC):

- with frequent attacks of biliary colic;
- with constant pain and dyspeptic syndrome (treatment methods: chemical, shock wave lithotripsy, as well as classical cholecystectomy or its laparoscopic variant).

3. Latent form, often manifested by pancreatic attacks, acute forms of pancreatitis.

4. Cholelithiasis of the intrahepatic bile ducts (mainly pigmented gallstones).

5. Complications of gallbladder: "disconnected" gallbladder, dropsy, empyema, perforation, gallbladder fistula, obstructive jaundice, acute or chronic recurrent pancreatitis.

6. Condition after cholecystectomy for cholelithiasis (absence of clinical manifestations of the disease after 6-12 months or more).

7. Postcholecystectomy syndrome:

- cholangiohepatitis;
- chronic recurrent or chronic pancreatitis with exocrine pancreatic insufficiency;
- recalculation of the gallbladder stump;
- the occurrence of stones in the intrahepatic bile ducts.

As you can see, in each of the above classifications, important clinical features of gallstone disease were emphasized - the pre-stone period, the latent form (stone bearing). However, in the years when these classifications were created, lithogenic changes in bile could be detected only by sampling it during duodenal intubation, and the latent flow - when using the X-ray method, which made diagnosis difficult. The situation has changed with the introduction of ultrasound (ultrasound) of the abdominal organs into widespread practice. In addition, a number of terminological concepts used in these classifications have been revised recently.

One of the latest classifications of gallstone disease was developed at the Central Research Institute of Gastroenterology (Moscow) and recommended by the 3rd Congress of the Scientific Society of Gastroenterologists of Russia (2003) for use in the clinic

Stage I - the first step, or preliminary stone.

A Bile that is thick and varied.

B. Biliary sludge formation:

- in conjunction with microliths

- with putty bile present;
- in the presence of both putty bile and microliths.

Stage II - the formation of gallstones.

A. By localization:

- in the gallbladder;
- in the common bile duct;
- inside the liver ducts.

B. Based on the quantity of stones:

- single;
- numerous.

C. By structure:

- cholesterol;
- pigmented;
- combined.

D. Based on the clinical course:

- a) hidden course;
- b) in the event that clinical signs are present:
 - in a painful form that resembles ordinary hepatic pain;
 - in a dyspeptic form;
 - appearing as other illnesses.

Stage III - calculous cholecystitis that is persistently recurring

Stage IV - complications.

The authors of the classification stipulate that the formation of JCB does not always go through the successive stages.

So, complications of the disease can be observed at any stage, including at its first stage.

The Ukrainian Association for the Study of Liver Diseases (2010) came out with a recommendation for use in clinical practice of the following classification of gallstones:

-Clinical course

asymptomatic (latent)

symptomatic

-Stage for the presence of gallstones

biliary sludge (pre-stone)

stone (s) (stone) *

-number of stones

single

multiple

-localization

gall bladder

bile ducts **

-Complications

cholecystitis:

acute

chronic

empyema of the gallbladder

peri-vesicular abscess

acute perforation of the gallbladder or cystic duct

gallbladder fistula

dropsy of the gallbladder

-holangitis:

acute

chronic

-mechanical jaundice

strictures of the bile ducts and sphincter of Oddi

Mirizzi syndrome

perforation of the common bile duct

common bile duct fistula

cholangiogenic abscesses

bowel obstruction due to gallstone

biliary pancreatitis

* The name of the stone stage is not included in the diagnosis, only its characteristics are indicated by the number and localization of gallstones.

** If possible, indicate which ones.

Rare forms of cholecystitis.

1. Anaerobic streptococci causing gas cholecystitis following blockage of the cystic duct or artery.

2. Typhoid cholecystitis (a condition in which the liver excretes typhoid bacilli from the bloodstream. Leech in 0.2% of patients with abrasive typhoid, this leads to infection of the biliary tract).

A. urgent

B. Chronic

3. Acute cholecystitis in AIDS is associated with stagnation of bile and an increase in its lithogenicity in critical conditions, with opportunistic microorganisms, including CMV cytomegalovirus and cryptosporidia, vascular insufficiency against the background of edema and infection.

4. Actinomycosis of the gallbladder, giardiasis of the biliary tract.

5. When cytotoxic medications like floxuridine are continuously infused into the hepatic artery, the condition known as chemical cholecystitis results.

6. Cholesterosis of the gallbladder, a condition in which lipids, including cholesterol esters, accumulate in the cells of the gallbladder's submucosa and epithelium. Raising the amount of cholesterol in the bile rather than the blood is linked to osteopenia. Cholesterosis is associated with an increase in cholesterol levels in the bile and not in the blood.

7. Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis, which is represented by a diffuse or localized destructive-inflammatory process involving macrophages loaded with lipids.

Pathogenesis.

There are 4 types of calculi:

cholesterol stones, containing about 95% cholesterol and a little bilirubin lime;

pigment stones, consisting mainly of bilirubin lime, cholesterol in them less than 30%;

mixed, cholesterol-pigment-calcareous stones,

lime stones containing up to 50% calcium carbonate and some other components (Pic. 4; 5).

JCB is a symptomatic complex, including not only the formation of stones, but the presence of typical biliary colic, then the pathogenesis of the latter is the advancement of the stone, spasm and obstruction of the biliary tract. Stones located in the area of the bottom and body of the gallbladder are usually not clinically manifested, ie are "dumb" -25-35% of persons of both sexes after 65 years are such "carriers".

CONCLUSION

The development of mechanical obstruction of the bile ducts, which is indicated by the appearance of icteric coloration of the skin and sclera in the patient, is associated with a large group of pancreatic and bile system diseases. This development, mistakenly, led to the combination of all these diseases. It was known as "obstructive jaundice" when it was first used in clinical settings. It has since been discovered that jaundice is merely a symptom of the illness, albeit jaundice usually develops into jaundice disease due to long-term, permanent mechanical obstruction of the bile tract. This is because cholestasis causes abnormalities in the development of some organs. The number of people suffering from pancreatic and major biliary tract illnesses has considerably increased recently.

To sum up, diseases of the gallbladder and biliary tract can affect people of all ages, but they are most common in adults. In children, diseases of the gallbladder and biliary tract are rare, but they

can be serious. It is important to be aware of the symptoms of these diseases and to seek medical attention if you experience any of them.

Early diagnosis and treatment of diseases of the gallbladder and biliary tract is important to prevent serious complications. Treatment options may include medication or surgery, depending on the type of disorder.

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